

AN OPEN LABELLED RCT STUDY TO ASSESS THE COMBINED EFFECT OF VIRECHANA, UTTARA BASTI, SARIVACHATUSHKA RASAYANA WITH AMRITAPRASHA GHRITA ANUPANA OVER ONLY KUSHTAKOKILAKSHADI RASAYANA WITH AMRITAPRASHA GHRITA ANUPANA IN KSHEENASHUKRA (OLIGOASTHENOZOOSPERMIA)

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ABSTRACT

Ksheenashukra, Vata–Pitta predominant condition, characterized by reduced semen quantity and motility and it can correlate with Oligoasthenozoospermia as per contemporary medicine. Conventional assisted reproductive techniques are costly and invasive, Whereas *Ayurveda* offers a holistic approach through *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* therapies. This prospective, open-labelled, randomized controlled clinical trial evaluated and compared the efficacy of *Shodhanottara Rasayana (Virechana, Uttara Basti, and Sariva Chatushka Rasayana with Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana)* and *Shamana Rasayana (Kushta Kokilakshadi Rasayana with Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana)* over a period of 48 days. Objective parameters such as semen volume, sperm count, and motility, along with subjective symptoms including *Daurbalya, Panduta, Mukhashosha, sadana, shrama, klaibhya*, etc were assessed before and after treatment using paired and unpaired t-tests. Both groups showed statistically significant improvement; however, Group A demonstrated highly

significant enhancement ($p < 0.001$) in seminal parameters and superior symptomatic relief compared to Group B. Additionally, conception occurred in seven participants during the study improvement of fertility potential noted. The findings suggest that *Shodhanottara Rasayana* offers faster and more effective outcomes by *Vata shamana*, *Shukravaha Sroto shodhana*, and rejuvenating *Shukra Dhatu*, while *Shamana Rasayana* is beneficial with a longer treatment duration, supporting the role of *Ayurvedic Rasayana* therapy as a safe and holistic management option for *Ksheenashukra* (oligoasthenozoospermia).

KEYWORDS: *Ksheenashukra*; Oligoasthenozoospermia; *Rasayana*; *Virechana*; *Uttarabasti*; *Amritaprasha Ghrita*; *Sarivachatushka*; *Kushtakokilakshadi Rasayana*.

INTRODUCTION

Oligoasthenozoospermia^[1] is a condition characterized by reduced sperm concentration (<15 million/ml), decreased sperm motility (<40%) and a major cause of male infertility. In *classics*, this condition closely correlates with *Ksheenashukra*,^[2] one among *Ashtavidha Shukra Dushti*, predominantly vitiation of *Vata* and *Pitta doshas*, leading to qualitative and quantitative depletion of *Shukra Dhatu* and impaired reproductive capacity. Classical texts advocate *Shodhana* therapies such as *Virechana* and *Basti* procedures, including *Uttara Basti*, for the management of *Ksheenashukra*. Epidemiology indicates approximately 45% of infertile males^[3] suffer from Oligoasthenozoospermia, highlighting clinical relevance of the condition.

Among *Panchakarma*, *Virechana* is *Pitta Rechaka* and *Vatanulomaka*, *Vikruta Doshashamaka*, while *Ardhamatrika Basti*^[4] is described as *Paramavrishya*, providing rapid improvement in *Agni Bala*, *Sharira Bala*, and prevents *punaragamana*. *Uttarabasti*^[5] is transurogenital drug delivery system, directly acts on the urogenital tract and specifically indicated in *Shukra Dushti* for improving both semen quality and quantity.

Regarding *Shamanoushadhi*, *Sariva*^[6] (*Hemidesmus indicus*) possesses *Shukrala*, *Rasayana*, and *Brimhana* properties due to *Madhura-Tikta Rasa*, *Sheeta Virya*, *Snigdha Guna*, and *Madhura Vipaka*. *Sariva Chatushka*, comprising four varieties of *Sariva*, raise the possibility of synergistic *Shukrala* action. *Amritaprasha Ghrita*,^[7] indicated in *Nashta Shukra*, acts as a potent *Rasayana* and *Brimhana* formulation, supporting restoration of *Shukra Dhatu*.

For comparative clinical feasibility, *Shamana Rasayana* approach using *Kushtakokilakshadi Rasayana*-containing *Kushta*,^[8] *Kokilaksha*^[9] *Amalaki*^[10] and *Pippali*^[11]-along with *Amritaprasha Ghrita* as a *Anupana*. These drugs are well documented for *Vrishya* and *Shukrala* properties and are suitable for outpatient practice. Present study therefore aims to compare the efficacy of *Shodhanottara Rasayana* (*Virechana* and *Uttarabasti* followed by *Sarivachatushka Rasayana* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita*) with *Shamana Rasayana* alone in improving semen parameters assessed by Computer Assisted Semen Analysis (CASA) in *Ksheenashukra* (oligoasthenozoospermia).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To Assess the Combined Effect of *Deepana, pachana, shukrala* with *Tamboolasava, Virechana, Ardhamatrikbasti, Uttarabasti* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita Sarivachatushka Rasayana* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana* in *Ksheenashukra* (Oligoasthenozoospermia).
2. To Assess the combined effect of *Deepana Pachana Shukrala* of *Tamboolasava, Sadyovirechana*, Effect of only *Kustakokilakshadi Rasayana* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana* in *Ksheenashukra* (Oligoasthenozoospermia)
3. To Compare the Combined Effect of *Tamboolasava, Virechana, Ardhamatraka basti, Uttara Basti* with *Amrutaprasha ghrita, Sarivachatushka Rasayana* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana* over only *Tamboolasava, Sadyovirechana, Kushtakokilakshadi Rasayana* with *Amritaprasha Ghrita Anupana* in *Ksheenashukra* (Oligoasthenozoospermia)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design- Prospective, open-labelled, randomized controlled clinical trial to evaluate the efficacy of *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy in comparison with *Shamana Rasayana* therapy in the management of *Ksheenashukra* (Oligoasthenozoospermia). study duration was 48 days with 15 days of follow-up period.

Sample Size and Randomization- Total 40 male patients. diagnosed with Oligoasthenozoospermia were randomly allocated into two groups of 20 patients each.

Diagnostic Criteria- Based on classical features of *Ksheenashukra* such as *Dourbalya, Mukhashosha, Panduta, Sadana, Shrama*, and *Klaibya*, along with semen analysis parameters

assessed by Computer Assisted Semen Analysis (CASA), including sperm count <15 million/ml and total motility <40%.

Inclusion Criteria- Male patients aged between 21 and 50 years, diagnosed with Oligoasthenozoospermia, fulfilling CASA criteria, fit for *Virechana* and *Basti* procedures, and willing to provide written consent.

Exclusion Criteria- Patients with azoospermia, congenital anomalies of the reproductive system, genetic disorders such as Klinefelter's syndrome, cryptorchidism, bilateral absence of vas deferens, and severe systemic illnesses were excluded.

Intervention

Group A – *Shodhanottara Rasayana* Group.

TREATMENT	MEDICINE	DURATION
<i>Deepana pachana Shukrala</i>	<i>Tambulasava</i> ^[12] 15ml Bice a day after food with- <i>ushnajala</i> as <i>anupana</i>	1st day to 48thDay
<i>Snehapana</i>	<i>Amritaprasha ghritam</i> 50ml on first day, 75ml for next 3days	6th day to 9th day
<i>Abhyanga & swedana</i>	<i>Sarvanga abhyanga</i> with <i>moorchita tila tailam</i> followed by <i>Baspa sveda</i>	10th day to 12th day
<i>Virechana karma</i>	<i>Eranda tailam</i> 50ml with 50 ml of milk	13th day
<i>Ardhamatrika Basti</i> as <i>poorva karma</i> for <i>uttaravasti</i>	<i>Ardhamatrika Basti</i> on 14th, 18th and 22nd Day morning after bladder and bowel evacuation	14th day, 18th day and 22nd Day
<i>Uttara basti</i>	<i>Amrita-prasha ghrita</i> 45 ml on 14th,, 18th and 22nd Day afternoon on the day of administration of <i>Ardhamatrika basti</i>	14th day, 18th day and 22nd day
<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Sarivachatushka rasayana</i> 500mg 2capsules BD, before food with <i>Amritaprasha gritam</i> 20ml with <i>ushna jala</i> as <i>anupana</i>	23rd day to 48th day

Group B – *Shamana Rasayana* Group.

TREATMENT	MEDICINE	DURATION
<i>Tambulasava</i>	<i>Tambulasava</i> 15ml Bice a day after food with- <i>ushnajala</i> as <i>anupana</i>	1 ST to 7 TH day
<i>Sadyovirechana</i>	<i>Payasa Eranda tailam</i> ^[13] 50ml with 50ml of milk	8 TH day
<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Kushtakokilakshadi Rasayana</i> 500mg 2 capsules bd with <i>Amritaprasha gritam</i> 20 ml with hot water as <i>anupana</i>	9 TH day to 48th day

Drug Preparation- Formulations including *Tambulasava*, *Amritaprasha Ghrita*, *Sarivachatushka Rasayana*, and *Kustakokilakshadi Rasayana* were prepared as per classical references following standard procedures.

Assessment Criteria

Subjective Parameters

Clinical features of *Ksheenashukra*^[14,15,16] like *Dourbalya*, *Mukhashosha*, *Panduta*, *Sadana*, *Shrama*, *Klaibya*, *Shukra-avisarga*, *Medra-vrishana vedana* and sexual parameters^[17] like sexual desire, erection, ejaculation, orgasm were assessed by graded scoring system before and after treatment.

Objective Parameters

CASA-based semen parameters:;) semen volume, sperm concentration, and motility were assessed. Routine hematological investigations, hormonal profile (serum testosterone, FSH, TSH, prolactin), and imaging studies were carried out to rule out associated pathologies.

Assessment Schedule

Assessments performed at baseline (BT), after completion of *Uttarabasti* (DT), and after completion of *Rasayana* therapy (AT).

Statistical Analysis

Data analyses using paired and unpaired *t*-tests. A *p*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

GHRITA MURCHANA

Ghrita Murchana Dravya

Kalka and Drava Dravya
of Murchana

DuringPaka

Attainment of Sneha
Siddhi Lakshana

Varti laskshana

Murchita Ghrita

Preparation of Amritaprasha ghrita

Murchita ghrita

Adding of kalka dravya

Adding of vidarikanda kashaya

Adding of amalaki kashaya

Adding of Ikshu rasa

Adding of Mamsa rasa

Adding of godugdha

Sneha paka

Amritaprasha ghrita

UTTARA BASTI PROCEDURE

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Total 42 subjects were registered for study, of which 40 patients (95.23%) completed the trial—20 in each group, indicating good compliance and acceptability of the interventions.

Demographic Profile

The age group ranging from 26 to 50 years, majority (42.5%) belonging to the 31–35 years age group, followed by 36–40 years (25%). All participants were married (100%) and belonged to *Madhyama Vaya*. Most subjects were from the Hindu community (92.5%). Occupational distribution showed predominance of physically and mentally demanding professions such as labourers, farmers, engineers, and business personnel, suggesting

occupational stress as a contributory factor. Economically, the majority belonged to the upper middle class (62.5%), followed by the lower middle class (27.5%).

Lifestyle and Dietary Factors

A mixed dietary pattern observed in 90% of participants. Addiction history in 50% of Group A and 35% of Group B participants had no addictive habits, while the remaining subjects reported alcohol, smoking, tobacco, or mixed habits. History of masturbation present in 87.5% of subjects. Dietary intake of *Katu*, *Tikta*, and *Kashaya Rasa* was reported by 42.5% of participants. *Divaswapna* and *Ratrijagarana* were observed in 37.5% and 32.5% of subjects respectively, indicating lifestyle irregularities.

Ayurvedic Constitutional Profile

Prakruti analysis revealed a predominance of *Vata–Kapha* (52.5%) and *Vata–Pitta* (35%) constitutions. Most participants exhibited *Madhyama Sara* (57.5%), *Pravara Satva* (57.5%), *Madhyama Satmya* (50%), *Madhyama Samhanana* (50%), and *Pravara Pramana* (47.5%). *Agni* and *Bala* showed variable *Abhyavarana* and *Jarana Shakti*, with a proportion having *Avara Vyayama Shakti* (45%).

Clinical Features of *Ksheenashukra*

The most commonly observed symptoms were *Dourbalya* (75%) and *Mukhashosha* (75%), followed by *Shrama* (42.5%), *Klaibya* (40%), and *Sadana* (37.5%). Other features such as *Panduta* (22.5%), *Medra-Vrishana Vedana* (15%), *Shukra Avisarga* (12.5%), *Asakthi Maithuna* (10%), and *Chirad Praseka* (10%) were less frequently reported. Primary infertility was predominant (75%), while secondary infertility was noted in 25% of cases. Premature ejaculation was present in 22.5% of participants.

Investigations

Ultrasonography revealed Varicocele as most common abnormality (30%), followed by Hydrocele (10%) and reduced testicular volume (5%). Hormonal evaluation showed testosterone abnormalities in 45% of participants, followed by LH (25%), FSH (20%), and prolactin (5%).

Baseline Semen Profile

Most participants had greyish-white semen (87.5%) with alkaline pH (100%) and increased viscosity (87.5%). Semen volume was >2.5 ml in 42.5% of subjects. Liquefaction time within

normal limits (≤ 20 minutes) in 52.5% of cases. Baseline sperm count predominantly 5–10 million/ml (45%), with 30% having counts < 5 million/ml. Sperm motility ranged between 5–25% (57.5%), and sperm immotility of 61–70% was observed in 42.5% of participants, confirming oligoasthenozoospermia.

Study Population and Completion Status

Total of 42 subjects, with open-labelled randomized controlled clinical study, with 21 subjects allocated to each group. Among them, 20 subjects (95%) from Group A and 20 subjects (95%) from Group B completed the study protocol. One subject from each group (5%) discontinued due to personal reasons, resulting in a total dropout rate of 4.76%. Thus, data from 40 subjects (95.23%) were included for final statistical analysis.

Age Distribution

Participants ranged 26 and 50 years of age. The majority belonged to the 31–35 years age group (42.5%), followed by 36–40 years (25%). Smaller proportions were observed in the 26–30 years (20%), 41–45 years (10%), and 46–50 years (2.5%) categories.

Religion

The majority of participants were Hindu (92.5%), while 7.5% belonged to the Muslim community. No influence of religious dominancy.

Occupation

In Group A, participants were mainly Engineers and farmers (15% each), followed by teachers, medical representatives, labourers, and businessmen (10% each). In Group B, labourers constituted the largest group (30%), followed by farmers (15%), while other occupations each accounted for 5%. Occupational stress, exertion may contribute to *Shukrakshaya*.

Marital Status

All participants in both groups were married (100%), which is relevant as infertility evaluation requires active marital life.

Socioeconomic Status

Most subjects belonged to the upper middle class (62.5%), followed by lower middle class (27.5%). Only a small proportion belonged to rich (7.5%) and poor (2.5%) socio-economic groups.

Dietary Pattern

Mixed diet predominant among (90%) participants, while only 10% followed a vegetarian diet. Intake of mixed diet, often associated with irregular dietary habits, may influence *Agni* and *Shukra Dhatu*.

Addiction History

In Group A, 50% no addictions, while remaining participants reported alcohol consumption, smoking, or combined habits. In Group B, 35% had no addictions, whereas alcohol (25%), tobacco (20%), smoking (10%), and combined habits (10%) were observed. Addictions are known contributors to *Shukra Dushti*.

Prakruthi

Vata–Kapha Prakruti (52.5%), *Vata–Pitta* (35%) and *Pitta–Kapha* (12.5%). *Vata* dominance is significant in the pathogenesis of *Ksheenashukra*.

Sara

Madhyama Sara (57.5%), *Pravara Sara* (27.5%) and *Avara Sara* (15%).

Satva

Pravara Satva in 57.5% of participants, *Madhyama Satva* in 30%, and *Avara Satva* in 12.5%.

Satmya

Madhyama Satmya was predominant (50%), followed by *Pravara* (37.5%) and *Avara Satmya* (12.5%).

Samhanana

Madhyama Samhanana in 50% of participants, followed by *Pravara* (35%) and *Avara* (15%).

Pramana

Pravara Pramana in 47.5%, *Madhyama* in 32.5%, and *Avara* in 20% of subjects.

Abhyavarana Shakti

Distribution almost equal among *Pravara* (32.5%), *Madhyama* (35%), and *Avara* (32.5%) categories.

Jarana Shakti

Both *Pravara* and *Avara Jarana Shakti* were equally observed (37.5% each), while 35% exhibited *Madhyama Jarana Shakti*.

Vyayama Shakti

Avara Vyayama Shakti was predominant (45%).

Vaya

Participants belonged to *Madhyama Vaya* (100%), correlates with reproductive phase of life.

Ksheenashukra Lakshana

Common symptoms included *Dourbalya* and *Mukhashosha* (75% each), followed by *Shrama* (42.5%), *Klaihya* (40%), *Sadana* (37.5%), and *Panduta* (22.5%).

Type of Infertility

Primary infertility (75%), while secondary infertility in 25% of participants.

Sexual History

History of masturbation in 87.5% of participants. Premature ejaculation in 22.5% of subjects.

Secondary Sexual Characters

Participants exhibited secondary sexual characters (100%).

USG Findings

Varicocele was the most common finding (30%), followed by hydrocele (10%) and reduced testicular volume (5%).

Hormonal Profile

Testosterone abnormalities were most prevalent (45%), followed by LH (25%), FSH (20%), and prolactin (5%).

Semen Parameters

- **Appearance:** Mostly greyish white (87.5%)
- **Volume:** Majority had >2.5 ml (42.5%)
- **Liquefaction time:** Normal in 52.5%
- **pH:** Alkaline in all subjects (100%)
- **Viscosity:** Increased in 87.5%

- **Sperm count:** 5–10 million/ml (45%)
- **Motility:** Poor motility (5–25%) in 57.5%
- **Immotility:** 61–70% immotile sperms in 42.5%

SUBJECTIVE AND OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

SI. NO	Parameter	Improvement in Group A	Improvement in Group B	Significance
1.	<i>Dourbalya</i>	53.70%	53.49%	Both significant; Group A slightly better
2.	<i>Mukhashosha</i>	66.81%,	63.41%,	Group B showed higher improvement after treatment
3.	<i>Panduta</i>	20%,	52.38%,	Significant improvement in Group B after treatment
4.	<i>Sadana</i>	58.08%,	55.81%,	Both improved; Group A slightly higher %
5.	<i>Shrama</i>	60.83%,	58.70%,	Both improved; Group A slightly higher %
6.	<i>Klaibhya</i>	62.22%,	58.70%,	Early improvement higher in Group A
7.	<i>Medra-Vrishana Vedana</i>	73.64%,	68.97%,	Early improvement higher in Group A
8.	<i>Shukra Avisarga</i>	Not fully provided in text	—	—
9.	Sexual Desire	59.13%	55.81%	Significant improvement in Group A than group B
10.	Penile Erection	43.75%	58.70%	* Significant improvement in Group B after treatment
11.	Semen Ejaculation	43.75%	55.88%	Significant improvement in Group B after treatment
12.	Orgasm	34.09%	50.00%	Significant improvement in Group B after treatment
13.	Semen Volume	50.13%	11.81%	Early improvement higher in Group A
14.	Semen Appearance	Normalized 100%	Normalized 100%	NS(p=1.000) Both treatment were effective
15.	Semen Viscosity	Normalized 100%	Normalized 100%	NS (p=1.000) Both treatment were effective
16.	Liquification Time	33.85%	14%	Significant improvement in Group A than group B
17.	Count	544%	338%	Significant improvement in Group A than group B
18.	Motility	111.62%	78.02%	Significant improvement in Group A than group B

DISCUSSION

Kṣheenashukra a *Vata–Pittaja Shukraduṣṭhi* characterized by both quantitative and qualitative depletion of *Shukra dhatu*, clinically correlate to Oligoasthenozoospermia. Vitiating of *Apana* and *Vyana Vata* leads to reduced sperm count and motility, Aggravated *Pitta*, with its *uṣhṇa* and *kṣhapana guṇas*, further depletes *snigdha* and *sthira guṇa* of *Shukra*. Combined imbalance of *Chala guṇa* of *Vata*, *Sara guṇa* of *Pitta*, and altered *Kapha guṇa* disrupts *Dhatu Poshana Shukra karma*, resulting in *Dhatukṣhaya* and *Shukravaha srotas dushti*.

Oligoasthenozoospermia, Major cause of male infertility worldwide. Management of *Kṣheenashukra*, based on *Nidana Parivarjana*, *Samshamana*, and *Samshodhana Chikitsa*. *Snehapana* with medicated *ghṛitas* plays a pivotal role due to its *Bṛimhaṇa*, *Vatahara*, *Vṛiṣhya*, and *Rasayana* actions, replenishing depleted *dhatu*s and correcting *Dhatu-pariṇama paka*. *Sarvanga Abhyanga* and *Baṣṭha Sweda* improve circulation, *srotorodha hara*, enhance hormonal balance, and support spermatogenesis. *Virechana* eliminates aggravated *Pitta* and *Rakta dushti*, restores *Agni*, clears *Ama*, and facilitates proper nourishment of *Shukra dhatu* while also providing mental clarity and stress reduction.

Tambulasava, mentioned in *Gadanigraha* is primarily indicated for *Deepana* and *Pachana karma* and used as *Purvakarma* in *Shodhana Chikitsa*. Beyond its *Agnivardhaka* and *Amapachaka* actions, *Tambulasava* is potent *Shukrajanana* and *Rasayana Yoga*, enhances both *matra* (quantity) and *guṇa* (quality) of *Shukra*. Formulation works through *Agni Deepana*, *Doṣha Shamana*, and *Dhatu Poshana*, thereby promoting *Shukra Vriddhi* and *Virya Vardhana*.

Pippali acts as excellent *Agnideepaka* and *Rasayana Dravya*, improving *Dhatu Sarata* and facilitating proper *Dhatuparinama* leading to *Shukra Dhatu Utpatti*. It balances *Pitta* and *Kapha Doṣas*, alleviating *Srotorodha* and enhancing *Shukravaha Srotas* patency, thereby improving *Shukra Gati* (motility). *Triphala* acts as *Amapachaka*, *Shothahara*, and *Vayasthapana Dravya*, detoxifies system, normalizes *Agni*, and creates a conducive environment for *Shukra Dhatu Poshana*.

Nagakesara exhibits *Raktaprasadana* and *Virya Vardhaka* properties by enhancing *Rakta Dhatu Sarata* and promoting microcirculation to *Shukravaha Srotas*. *Tambula (Puga Patra)*

possesses *Katu-Tikta Rasa*, *Uṣṇa Virya*, and *Katu Vipaka*, which promote *Dipana- Pachana* and *Doṣha Shamana*, specially *Kapha-Vata*.

Thus, by performing *Agni Dipana*, *Ama Pachana*, *Doṣha Saṁyamana*, *Srotoshodhana*, and *Shukra Dhatu Poshana*, *Tambulasava* acts as a *Balya*, *Vṛiṣhya*, and *Rasayana Yoga*, enhancing Sperm count (*Shukra Vriddhi*) and Motility (*Shukra Gati*), making it an effective formulation in *Kṣheenashukra* and other *Shukra Dushti Vikaras*.

Discussion on *Amritaprasha ghrta*- Mentioned in *Charaka Chikitsasthana (KṣhataKṣheena Chikitsa)*, specifically indicated in *Nashta Shukra*. It is administered in the form of *Snehapana*, *Uttarabasti*, and *Anupana*. This formulation is rich *Jivaniya Varga Dravyas*, plays vital role in *Rasadi Dhatu Poshana* and restores *Dhatu Samyata*, by rejuvenating *Shukra Dhatu*.

The formulation contains *Ashwagandha* and *Shatavari*, having *Medhya*, *Rasayana*, and *Shukrala karma*, which promote *Shukra Dhatu. Vriddhi*, enhances *Virya*, and strengthens *Garbha Sambhavana Shakti. Kapikacchu* acts as a potent *Vṛiṣhya* and *Shukrala Dravya*, improving *Shukra Matra* (quantity), *Shukra Guṇa* (quality), and *Shukra Gati* (motility). *Pippali*, is *Uṣṇa*, *Laghu*, *Tikṣhṇa*, enhances *Agni Dipana* and *Dhatu Sarata*, increases *sara guna* of *Pitta* and *Chala guna* of *vata* while reducing the *Snigdha* and *Picchilata* of *Kapha Doṣha*, thus promotes better *Shukra Pravaha* (movement of semen) and *Gati* (Motility).

Dravyas like *Bala*, *Arjuna*, *Ashoka*, *Mṛidvika*, and *Mamṣa Rasa* act as *Bṛiṁhaṇa*, *Balya*, and *Vatanulomana*, *Shukra Dhatu Samyata. Kṣhaya Janya Samprapti* seen in *Kṣheenashukra*. These *dravyas* nourish *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*, are the *Upadana Bhutas* for *Shukra Dhatu*.

In *Kṣheenashukra*, It promotes *Agni deepana* and *Amapachana* by improving *Ahara Rasa Nirmiti*. Through *Doṣha Saṁyamana*, it balances *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*, particularly pacifying *Vata*, which is predominant in *Shukra kshaya*. Its *Srotoshodhana* action clears *avarodha*

The *Rasayana* and *Bṛiṁhaṇa Karma* nourishes *Shukra dhatu*. Ultimate actions are *Shukra Vardhana* and *Virya Vardhana*, enhances structural and functional capacity of *Shukra Dhatu*.

Ardhamatrika Basti administered prior *Uttarabasti* acts as a *Vriṣhya* and *Balya*. by pacifying *Vata*, enhancing *Agni*, nourishing *Rasadi dhatus*, alleviates symptoms such as *dourbalya*, *shrama*, *mukhashoṣha*, *pañḍuta*, and *klaibhya*.

Discussion on Sarivachatushka rasayana

Four botanical varieties of sariva —*Hemidesmus indicus*, *Ichnocarpus frutescens*, *Decalepis hamiltonii*, and *Cryptolepis buchanani*-were selected for present study, These having *Guru*, *Snigdha*, and *Madhura Guna*, enhance the *Snigdha Guna* of *Kapha* and promote *Dhatu Samyata*. Their *Tikta Rasa* possesses *Shodhana*, Anti-microbial action of *sariva* helps in reducing subclinical reproductive tract infections.

Discussion on Kushtakokilakshadi rasayana

In Group B, formulation was administered as a *Rasayana Yoga*, containing *Kuṣṭha*, *Kokilakṣa*, *Amalaki*, and *Pippali*. *Katu*, *Tikta Rasa* of *Kuṣṭha* facilitate *Shukra Dhatu Shodhana*. *Amalaki*, with *sheeta*, *Rukṣha*, *Tikṣhṇa Guna* nourishes *Shukra Dhatu*, enhances *Sarata*, and balances *Pitta*, supporting proper *Dhatu Paripaka* and sperm maturation. By *Kashaya Rasa Shoshana karma* improves sperm motility by reducing *Snigdha* and *Pichila Guna* in reproductive channels and promotes effective *Spermatogenesis*. *Pippali* is *Agni Dipaka* and *Rasayana*, improves *Dhatu Sarata*, corrects metabolic imbalances, and supports *Shukra Vriddhi*.

Discussion on Uttarabasti

Mechanism of action of Uttarabasti

Uttarabasti is trans urogenital intra-vesicular drug delivery system used in males, where medicine is administered into the bladder through the urethra, remaining effective beyond the first urine voiding after installation. It acts on all the *srotas* (channels) by performing *Shodhana*, *Shamana*, and *Brimhana* functions. In classical texts, the application of *Uttarabasti* for the management of *Shukra Dushti* (semen dysfunction), emphasizing its importance in correcting abnormalities in *Shukravaha srotas*, which are responsible for semen production.

Administered through the *Shukravaha Srotomoola*, *Uttarabasti* restore the proper functioning of *srotas* and improve spermatogenesis. In case of *Shukra Dushti*, restoring the normal function of *Apana Vata* is crucial, governs the process of semen ejaculation. Conditions like varicocele, epididymal cyst, atherosclerosis, and venous occlusions in the penis can obstruct

the flow of *Apana Vata*, leading to dysfunction. *Uttarabasti* helps to address these issues by targeting urinary bladder, where *Apana Vata* is located, through its purgative action, thereby restoring sexual function.

OBSERVATIONS

Demographic Profile- In the present study, majority of subjects belonged to the 26–35 years, indicating a higher prevalence of *Kṣheenashukra* during early and mid-reproductive age. May attributed to *Shukra-duṣṭikara nidānas* such as mental stress, improper diet, sedentary habits, and excessive sexual activity. Individuals 30–50 years, age-related hormonal decline combined with lifestyle factors further contributes to *Shukra Kṣhaya*.

Religion-wise distribution showed predominance of Hindu subjects, reflecting the regional population structure.

Occupational- revealed that most subjects were engaged in sedentary, stressful, or physically demanding jobs with exposure to heat, dust, and irregular routines. These factors, along with *Ati-vyayama*, *Manasika hetu*, and poor nutrition, aggravate *Vata* and *Pitta*, leading to *Shukra Dhatu Kṣhaya*.

All subjects were married, suggesting increased awareness and concern regarding fertility. Psychological stress, responsibilities, relationship issues, and excessive sexual activity may contribute to hormonal imbalance and impaired Spermatogenesis.

Dietary assessment showed predominance of mixed diet. Excessive intake of spicy, oily, fermented, and non-vegetarian food aggravates *Vata-Pitta*, causes *Agnimandya*, and hampers *Dhatu Poṣhaṇa*, leading to *Kṣheenashukra*.

Addiction to alcohol, smoking, and tobacco was common. substances having *Rukṣha*, *Uṣhṇa*, *Tikṣhṇa*, *Vyavayi*, and *Vikasa guṇas* antagonistic to *Shukra* and *Ojas*, resulting in oxidative stress, *Dhatu Kṣhaya*, *Srotorodha*, and impaired reproductive function.

Rogi-Roga Parikṣha

Predominance of *Vata-Pitta* and *Vata-Kapha Prakṛti* indicates susceptibility to *Shukra Kṣhaya* due to *Rukṣhata*, *Uṣhṇata*, and *Agnimandya*. Most subjects exhibited *Madhyama Sara*, *Satmya*, *Samhanana*, and *Pramaṇa*, offering partial resistance but insufficient protection against persistent *nidanas*.

Infertility and Sexual Factors

Primary infertility, due to *Shukra-duṣṭikara ahara-vihara*, psychological stress, and lack of fertility awareness.

Semen Parameters

Most subjects exhibited normal semen appearance and alkaline pH, indicating preserved accessory gland function. Reduced semen volume, delayed liquefaction, low sperm count, and poor motility were commonly observed.

Lifestyle Nidanas

Diwaswapna, *Ratrijagaraṇa*, and *atisevana* of *Katu-Tikta-Kaṣhaya rasa ahara* were significant contributors, causing *Vata-Pitta prakopa* and *Dhatu shoṣhaṇa*.

Socio-Economic Status

Most subjects belonged to the upper-middle class. SES influenced lifestyle stress and dietary habits but showed no statistical difference between groups.

DISCUSSION ON RESULTS

Kṣheenashukra, corresponding to Oligoasthenozoospermia, is primarily a condition of *Shukra Dhatu Kṣhaya* associated with *Vata–Pitta vitiation*, *Agnimandya*, *Ojo-kshaya*, and impaired *Shukravaha Srotas* function. The present open-labelled randomized controlled study evaluated the comparative efficacy of *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy and *Rasayana* therapy alone in restoring *Shukra Dhatu*, improving sexual function, and enhancing semen quality.

The overall findings of the study indicate that both treatment protocols were effective in improving subjective symptoms such as *Dourbalya*, *Sadana*, *Shrama*, *Mukhashoṣha*, *Klaibhya*, reduced libido, ejaculatory dysfunction, and orgasmic impairment, as well as objective semen parameters including volume, liquefaction time, sperm count, and motility.

Subjects treated with *Shodhanottara Rasayana* (Group A) showed earlier and more improvement in *dourbalya*, *mukhashoṣha*, *panduta*, *klaibhya*, *Shukra-avisarga*, *medra-vrishana vedana* and semen parameters. This rapid response can be attributed to the action of *Virechana*, which removes *Doṣha avaraṇa*, corrects *Agnimandya*, clears *Srotorodha*, and enhances *Dhatu* receptivity. By optimizing *Dhatavagni* and *Srotas* patency, *Shodhana*

facilitates better absorption and utilization of *Rasayana* drugs, resulting in faster restoration of *Dhatu Bala* and *Ojas*.

The *Rasayana* formulations used in Group A—*Amṛitaprasha Ghṛita*, *Tambulasava*, and *Sariva Chatuṣhka Rasayana* acted synergistically to nourishes *Rasa* and *Shukra Dhatus*, improves *Agni*, pacify *Vata–Pitta*, and promote *Ojas vardhana*. This combination resulted in significant improvement in semen volume, faster liquefaction, marked rise in sperm count, and better sperm motility, indicating enhanced Spermatogenesis and improved seminal environment. The improvement in semen appearance and maintenance of normal pH and viscosity further suggest restoration of physiological seminal gland function without disturbing semen homeostasis.

In contrast, subjects receiving *Kuṣhṭakokilakṣhadi Rasayana* alone (Group B) demonstrated slower onset of improvement, particularly in subjective parameters related to energy, libido, erection, and ejaculation. However, with continued therapy, this group showed substantial and sustained improvement, especially in sexual desire, erectile function, orgasm, *Paṇḍuta*, and long-term semen quality. The formulation, containing *Kuṣhṭa*, *Kokilakṣa*, *Gokṣura*, and *Ashwagandha*, possesses *Vṛiṣhya*, *Balya*, *Rasayana*, and *Ojovardhaka* properties, which gradually stabilize *Agni*, enhance *Dhatu* metabolism, and support continuous *Shukra Dhatu* replenishment.

A notable observation of the study is that parameters directly related to *Rakta Dhatu*, such as *Paṇḍuta*, responded better in the *Rasayana*-only group, whereas *Vata–Pitta* dominant and functional symptoms such as *dourbalya*, *mukhashosha*, *panduta* and early sexual dysfunction improved more rapidly in the *Shodhanottara* group. This suggests differential *Dhatu*-level action of the two treatment approaches, with *Shodhana* primarily facilitating rapid functional correction and *Rasayana* alone contributing to deeper structural nourishment over time.

Objective semen parameters showed significant improvement in both groups, with greater magnitude of increase in sperm count, motility, semen volume, and reduction in liquefaction time in the *Shodhanottara* group. This supports the *classical* principles that *Shodhana* enhances the efficacy of *Rasayana* therapy, particularly in conditions involving *Srotorodha* and *Dhatu Kṣhaya*. The maintenance of normal seminal pH and viscosity throughout the study in both groups confirms the safety and physiological compatibility of the interventions.

Overall, the study demonstrates that *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy offers faster symptomatic relief and superior early improvement in semen parameters, while *Rasayana* therapy alone provides gradual, sustained, and stable rejuvenation of *Shukra Dhatu*. Both approaches are effective and complementary, and their judicious application based on disease chronicity, strength of the patient, and *Dhatu* involvement may yield optimal results in the management of *Kṣheenashukra* (Oligoasthenozoospermia).

Mode of Action of Intervention

Kṣheenashukra is caused by *Shukra Dhatu Kṣhaya* associated with aggravated *Vata* and vitiated *Pitta*, resulting in increased *Rukṣa–Uṣhṇa guṇas*, *Srotorodha*, impaired *Shukravaha Srotas* function, and reduced Spermatogenesis. The present intervention was designed to achieve *Agni Deepana*, *Doṣha Shamana*, *Srotoshodhana*, *Dhatu Poṣhaṇa*, and *Rasayana–Vṛiṣhya* effects.

Tamboolasava, used as *Purvakarma*, enhances *Agni*, digests *Ama*, removes *Srotorodha*, and promotes *Shukra Vṛiddhi* by improving *Dhatu Pariṇama*. *Snehapana* with *Amṛitaprasha Ghṛita* restores *Snigdhatva*, pacifies *Vata*, nourishes *Shukra Dhatu*, enhances *Ojas*, and supports sperm count and motility.

Virechana with *Payasa Eraṇḍa Taila* eliminates vitiated *Pitta–Rakta Duṣṭi*, corrects *Vata Anulomana*, and improves *Shukra Matra*, *Guṇa*, and *Gati* through its *Snigdha*, *Bṛimhaṇa*, and *Vṛiṣhya* properties. *Ardhamatrika Basti* corrects *Vata Kopa*, strengthens *Agni* and *Dhatu*s.

Uttarabasti directly acts on *Apana Vata* and *Shukravaha Srotas*, clearing *srotorodha*, improving spermatogenesis, semen circulation, and ejaculatory function through targeted trans-urogenital drug delivery.

Sarivachatuṣhka Rasayana provides *Shodhana*, antimicrobial, and *Dhatu-poshaka* effects, supporting tissue nourishment and healthy spermatogenesis. *Kuṣṭhakokilakṣhadi Rasayana* in the control group improves semen quality through *Ama Pachana*, *Rasayana*, and *Shukrajanana* actions but with comparatively lesser efficacy.

Thus, *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy demonstrated superior results by addressing both *Doṣhic* imbalance and *Dhatu Kṣhaya*, leading to significant improvement in semen parameters and reproductive vitality in *Kṣheenashukra*.

CONCLUSION

Kṣheenashukra, a *Vata–Pitta* predominant disorder correlates with Oligoasthenozoospermia, characterized by reduced sperm count and motility, leading to male infertility. Conventional assisted reproductive techniques are costly, invasive, and often associated with variable success, highlighting need for effective, economical alternatives. The present study evaluated Ayurvedic interventions using *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy (Group A) and *Shamana Rasayana* therapy (Group B) in the management of *Kṣheenashukra*.

Both treatment groups shows improvement in subjective symptoms such as *Dourbalya*, *Mukhashoṣha*, *Paṇḍuta*, *sadana*, *shrama*, *klaibhya*, *Shukra-avisarga*, *medra-vrishana vedana* as well as objective semen parameters such as seminal volume, P^h count, motility. However, Group A, received *Shodhana* followed by *Rasayana* therapy, showed earlier and statistically significant improvement in semen volume, sperm count, and motility, indicating faster restoration of *Shukra Dhatu*. This can be attributed to effective *Agni Deepana*, *Srotoshodhana*, *Vata–Pitta Shamana*, and enhanced *Dhatu Poṣhaṇa* achieved through *Tamboolasava*, *Virechana*, *Basti*, *Uttarabasti*, *Sarivachatuṣhka Rasayana*, and *Amṛitaprasha Ghṛita*.

Group B, treated with *Kuṣhṭakokilakṣhadi Rasayana* and *Amṛitaprasha Ghṛita*, also showed meaningful improvement, over a longer duration. This highlights the role of *Shamana Rasayana* as a safe, effective, and practical OPD-based option, particularly intensive *Panchakarma* procedures are not feasible.

Overall, *Shodhanottara Rasayana* therapy is superior in achieving rapid and significant improvement in sperm quality and fertility potential, *Shamana Rasayana* shows gradual sustained benefits. Both approaches effectively enhanced male reproductive health, validating the role of *Ayurvedic* management in *Kṣheenashukra*. Notably, seven subjects achieved successful conception during the study, reflecting the clinical relevance of observed improvements in semen parameters.

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